

Organic Pesticides. Part XIII. Synthesis of Some New Fluoro-ketones and their Thiosemicarbazones

K. C. Joshi and S. Giri

Several new fluoro-ketones and their thiosemicarbazones have been prepared. Antifungal activity of five of the thiosemicarbazones has been evaluated against *Alternaria solani*.

The ketones, aldehydes, their semicarbazones, and thiosemicarbazones often exhibit interesting biological properties owing to the presence of toxophoric $>C=O$ and $>N-C-S$ groupings respectively. This is apparent from their use as larvicides¹, insecticides², fungicides, and bactericides³. It was therefore thought worthwhile to synthesise and study the pesticidal properties of some new fluoro-ketones and their thiosemicarbazones, as detailed information pertaining them seems lacking in the literature.

The fluoro-ketones have been prepared by the Friedel-Crafts acylation of appropriate hydrocarbons. On refluxing with an ethanolic solution of thiosemicarbazide⁴, the ketones have readily furnished the corresponding thiosemicarbazones.

Five representative thiosemicarbazones have been evaluated as antifungal chemicals against *Alternaria solani* by agar-plate technique.

EXPERIMENTAL

Fluoro-ketones

An appropriate hydrocarbon (1*M*) was subjected to the Friedel-Crafts reaction in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride (1.5*M*) and an acid chloride (1*M*). After decomposing the resulting complex with ice-cold HCl, the product separating was isolated by the usual procedure. The ketones thus obtained are listed in Table I.

Thiosemicarbazones of Fluoro-ketones

These were prepared according to the method of Scott and McCall⁴. A solution of an appropriate ketone (1*M*) in ethanol was treated with an ethanolic solution of thiosemicarbazide (1.1*M*). After refluxing for 20 to 30 minutes, the thiosemicarbazones were isolated by the usual method. These are recorded in Table II.

1. Siegler *et al.*, *J. Econ. Entomol.*, 1942, **35**, 74.

2. U. S. P. 2,426,349/1947.

3. Bau-Hoi *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 713.

4. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 1767.

TABLE I

No.	R.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	%Carbon.		%Hydrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
R=4-Fluoro-P.								
1.	2'-Chloro-P	58-59°	51%	C ₁₃ H ₈ OCIF	65.80	66.53	3.10	3.41
2.	4'-Nitro-P	180-82°	48	C ₁₃ H ₈ O ₃ FN	63.24	63.67	3.02	3.27
3.	3'-Chloro-P	126-27°	58	C ₁₃ H ₈ OCIF	65.92	66.53	3.21	3.41
4.	3'-Methyl-P	95-96°	52	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ OF	78.02	78.50	4.61	5.14
R=2-Fluoro-5-methoxy-P.								
5.	β-Pyridyl	120-21°	49	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₂ NF	67.01	67.53	4.31	4.33
R=4-Fluoronaphthyl.								
6.	2'-Chloro-P	162°	61	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ OCIF	71.01	71.70	3.22	3.51
7.	4'-Methoxy-P	229-30°	63	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₂ F	76.00	77.14	4.14	4.64
8.	β-Pyridyl	218-19°	47	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ ONF	75.74	76.49	3.28	3.98
9.	Phenyl	81-82°	69	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ OF	80.32	81.00	4.02	4.40
10.	Ethyl	110°	65	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ OF	77.49	77.22	5.24	5.44

N.B. P denotes phenyl.

TABLE II

No.*	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
				Found.	Reqd.
1	171°	60%	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₃ ClFS	9.48	10.40
2	167-68°	71	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₄ F	10.38	10.06
3	122-23°	62	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₃ ClFS	10.04	10.40
4	102-103°	54	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₃ FS	10.80	11.14
5	135-36°	49	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ ON ₄ FS	10.64	10.52
6	173-75°	64	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₃ ClFS	8.18	8.95
7	170°	43	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ ON ₃ FS	9.56	9.07
8	176-78°	50	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ NF ₄ S	9.06	9.87
9	148-50°	62	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₃ FS	9.13	9.90
10	160°	39	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₃ FS	11.02	11.63

*The number corresponds to that of ketone compound recorded in Table I.

Evaluation of Fungicidal Activity

The antifungal activity of the five thiosemicarbazones was evaluated against the fungus *Alternaria solani* by the agar-plate technique⁵.

The Difco potato dextrose agar of pH 5.6 was inoculated with the spores of *A. solani*. The inoculum was mixed with the melted, cooled agar, poured into sterilised petri plates, and allowed to harden. As soon as the agar had hardened, the test compound (approx. 0.1 g.) was placed over 1 cm² area on the surface of the agar. The plates were incubated for five days at 25°. At the close of the incubation period, the width of the zone of the inhibition surrounding each test compound was noted. The compounds were tested without dilution. The results of this screening are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

No.	Compound.	Width of zone of inhibition.
1	4-Fluoronaphthylphenyl-KT	10 mm
2	3-Chlorophenyl-4-fluorophenyl-KT	23
3	4-Nitrophenyl-4-fluorophenyl-KT	19
4	Ethyl-4-fluoronaphthyl-KT	9
5	β -Pyridyl-4-fluoronaphthyl-KT	10

N.B. KT denotes ketone thiosemicarbazone.

The results indicate that the compounds exhibit excellent fungicidal properties and they warrant further screening at higher dilutions and against a wider spectrum of fungi.

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